

Economic Empowerment and Women Entrepreneurship-A Study

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Abstract

The speedily varying economy has affected to endeavour out as entrepreneurs. The entrepreneurial activity for some gender is an economic need; while for others, a pure business endeavours though their numbers would be small, each, however, require a specific treatment. Only a small fraction of entrepreneurs, who is in to relatively high-end products, and those registered can avail of such support, while a vast majority of them remain without any assistance. effort should be made to bring unregistered enterprise into the fold of registered ones so that a large section of entrepreneurs can avail of the available policy concessions and benefits.

Keywords: concept, functions, problems, growth.

Introduction

Empowering women does not mean merely ensuring jobs and a place in political system for a few of them, though this is a welcome step, but going beyond this. The educated/under educated, poor and developed women really need empowerment. Economic improvement of women population not only would help the family but also the economy at large. While solutions to women on social front does boost their confidence, the economic empowerment would not only raise their confidence levels but would also enable them to become part of mainstream economy. While poverty alleviation programmes such as National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (NREG), ensuring minimum calories 'intake through subsidized supply of food items, etc. can address the problem largely but there is fear that these would make them dependents and may also encourage corruption at implementation level. In modern societies they have been confined to the four walls to participate in all sorts of activities. The global evidences buttress that women have been performing exceedingly well in different sphere of activities

Concept

The prospective role women entrepreneur in India has been realized since a long time. India history reveals that there has been several women like Rajia Sultan, Rani Laxmi Bai, Nur Jahan, and Rani Padmini who has successfully rules their kingdom. In modern india also several women leaders and administrators like Sarojini Naidu, Indira Gandhi, Vijaylaxmi Pandit who have succeeded in their salesmanship. All these prove that Indian women are in no way

inferior to men in all walks inferior to men in all way inferior to men in walks of life and they can be good entrepreneurs as men in the country.

Functions of Women Entrepreneurs

A women entrepreneur is expected to perform the following functions:

Risks

The women entrepreneur has to take risks in the form of changes in tastes of consumers, techniques of production and new innovations. Such risks can be minimized if women take earlier initiative, use skill and judgment.

Decision Making

The women entrepreneur has to decide thenature of type of products to be produced. She enters a particular industry which offers her the best prospects and products and produces those goods which she thinks will pay her the most and employees those methods of production which seems to her the most profitable.

Innovation

The women entrepreneur conceives the idea for the improvement in the quality of product line. She considers the economic viability and technological feasibility in bringing about improved quality.

Managerial Function

She formulates production plans, arranges finance, purchase raw materials, provides production amenities, organizes the sales and also undertakes the task of personal management. She undertakes adventure, assumes risk and earns profit. She is a woman who has a strong motivation to achieve success.

Growth and Development of Women Entrepreneurship

According to ministry of micro, small and medium enterprises women-owned enterprise accounted for just 14.20 percent of the total 20.3 million enterprise in the country in 2018-19. It is, however, important to know that more than 85 percent women entrepreneurs were operating as unregistered entities and apparently based in rural areas, perhaps an indication they are income-generating activity for self-family. Women enterprises were concentrated in sectors with particular ease of entry and low returns. This does not mean that women entrepreneurs are not into quality product/services, but their number would be relatively small. some category of women informally takes up business activities like academic and non academic coaching, fabric painting, making dresses, tailoring, etc., as part time activities as well as to supplement family income.

The forgoing observations about the constraints faced by women entrepreneurs pose many challenges to policy makers in improving the business environment for them.

To help women take active participation in the economy via enterprises, both the categories need firstly improved access to finance. Although MSMs are part of priority sector lending, women entrepreneurs do not get any facility.

Problems of Women Entrepreneurs

The basic problem of a women entrepreneur is that she is a woman. This is because of her dual responsibility towards family and workplace.

Family Involvement

Most of her time is devoted in the upliftment of the children and other members of the family married women entrepreneurs have to stricken a balance between the home and business.

Male Dominance

Equal treatment to men and women is absent at all levels in the society as well as at business level. There exists a male superiority ego complex with creates an obstacle in the road to success.

Lack of Education

The literacy rate among women India is quite low. Due to this lack of education women are unaware of the latest developments taking place in different areas of knowledge e.g., finance, marketing, accounts, competitors, etc.

Non Availability of Finance

Women entrepreneurs suffer from inadequate financial resources and working capital. Banks are reluctant to provide assistance to women because banks feel that these women may at any time leave their business and become housewives again.

Shortage of raw materials scarcity of raw materials and other inputs is one of the main reasons for the failure of the enterprise run by women. These women lack the capability to take the advantage of the market whether prices are low due to the shortage of working capital.

Severe Competition

Women entrepreneurs 'faces serve competition severe competition for their products from male dominated industries. The organizational set up is poor which is unable to pump the required funds at time.

No Risk Bearing Capacity

The most important pre-request for success in entrepreneurship is the risk bearing capacity. All throughout her life-time she has led protected life dominatedby the family members namely her parents,elder members in the family and after marriage her husband and in –laws. Hence at no time has she faced the risk of lifealone

Social attitude in a male dominates society women do not get equal treatmentinspire of the constitutional and legal equality.

Too much dependence on middlemen

The women entrepreneurs are mostly dependent on middlemen who take major share of the profits

Analysis the Women Entrepreneur in Tirunelveli District

Skills Preferred by Respondents

Skills	Beneficiaries	%
1. Stitching and tailoring	80	17.35
2. Faison designing	82	17.79
3.Agarbatti candles and soap manufacturing	25	5.42
4.Rexin bags manufacturing	45	9.76
5.Soft toys manufacturing	45	9.76
6.Various masala marketing	20	4.34

7.Cooking and catering	23	4.99
8.Computer education	45	9.76
9.Beauticians course	26	5.64
10.Boys fibre moulding	24	5.21
11.Decorative wax art	05	1.08
12.Creative painting	21	4.56
13.Embroidery, knitting, coochet	20	4.34
Total	461	100

Source: Helping foundation, Tirunelveli districtss

Series 1: %chance Series 2: Beneficiaries

It is known fact that fashion designing is a leading activities along with the stitching and tailoring among the mass section of population. cooking and catering which assumes to be the back-borne of the mass section of the female population indicates only 9.76 percent of the total 461 influx of females is notices more in the business of creative painting and soap manufacturing, beautician course rather than other skills.

The rural women are out of action due to various reasons,such as most of them socially background, illiterture, with low motivation and poor economic base. Individually, a ruralwomen is not only weak in socio economic term but also lacks access to the knowledge and information, which are the most important components of today’s process. However, in a group. They are empowered to conquer many of these weaknesses

Conclusion

The speedily varying economy has affected to endeavour out as entrepreneurs. The entrepreneurial activity for some gender is an economic need while for others a pure business endeavours though their numbers would be small, each, however, require a specific treatment. Only a small fraction of entrepreneurs, who is in to relatively high-end products, and those registered can avail of such support, while a vast majority of them remain without any assistance. effort should be made to bring unregistered enterprise into the fold of registered ones so that a large section of entrepreneurs can avail of the available policy concessions and benefits